

a Philips PR-9405 pH meter in aqueous medium (accuracy ± 0.02 pH).

The following sets of solutions, each of initial volume 50 ml and ionic strength $\mu = 0.1 M$ (NaClO_4), were prepared and pH-metrically titrated with a standard solution of $0.25 M$ NaOH: (a) $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ HClO_4 , (b) $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ $\text{HClO}_4 + 5 \times 10^{-4} M$ ligand (primary) + $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ metal ion (Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , or Zn^{II}), and (c) (a) $+ 5 \times 10^{-4} M$ ODAA + $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ secondary ligands + $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ metal ion. Some representation data are presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Potentiometric curves for nickel: (a) HClO_4 , (b) $\text{Ni}^{II} + (\text{a}) + \text{ODAA}$, (c) MALEA + (b), (d) MALNA + (b), and (e) PHA + (b).

Results and Discussion

The dissociation constants of the ligands were evaluated by Irving and Rossotti method⁶. The formation constants of the binary and ternary complexes were calculated by the method of Ramamoorthy and Santapa^{8,9}. The refined^{8,9} values are stated in Table 1.

TABLE I—FORMATION CONSTANTS* OF BINARY AND TERNARY COMPLEXES

System	log K_{MA}	System	log K_{MAB}
$\text{Ni}^{II} - \text{ODAA}$	3.32		
$\text{Cu}^{II} - \text{ODAA}$	3.80		
$\text{Zn}^{II} - \text{ODAA}$	3.52		
$\text{Ni}^{II} - \text{MALEA}$	2.00	$\text{Ni}^{II} - \text{ODAA} - \text{MALEA}$	7.32
$\text{Cu}^{II} - \text{MALEA}$	2.88	$\text{Zn}^{II} - \text{ODAA} - \text{MALEA}$	7.56
$\text{Zn}^{II} - \text{MALEA}$	2.00		
$\text{Ni}^{II} - \text{MALNA}$	3.24	$\text{Ni}^{II} - \text{ODAA} - \text{MALNA}$	5.48
$\text{Cu}^{II} - \text{MALNA}$	4.10	$\text{Cu}^{II} - \text{ODAA} - \text{MALNA}$	7.78
$\text{Zn}^{II} - \text{MALNA}$	2.96	$\text{Zn}^{II} - \text{ODAA} - \text{MALNA}$	6.76
$\text{Ni}^{II} - \text{PHA}$	2.17	$\text{Ni}^{II} - \text{ODAA} - \text{PHA}$	5.41
$\text{Cu}^{II} - \text{PHA}$	2.50	$\text{Cu}^{II} - \text{ODAA} - \text{PHA}$	6.75
$\text{Zn}^{II} - \text{PHA}$	2.20		

pK^H: ODAA (2.84, 4.94), MALEA (1.91, 5.52), MALNA (2.70, 5.02), PHA (2.81, 4.74). *Limits of error = $\pm 0.02 - 0.23$ in log units.

The potentiometric curves for all the metals were found to be very similar in nature and hence the curves of only one metal ion (Ni^{II}) are shown in

Fig. 1. For curve (a), inflection occurs at $m = 5.0$, therefore, for curve (b), the inflection is counted to take place at $m = 2[(7.0 - 5.0)]$. It indicates the formation of 1 : 1 complex in $\text{Ni}^{II} - \text{ODAA}$ system (m being the number of moles of base added per mole of metal ion or ligand). The curves (c-e) represent 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complex system, for which inflections were observed at $m = 4[(9.0 - 5.0)]$. These 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complexes result from stepwise addition of ligands to the metal ion. The formation of heteroligand-metal complexes in these systems is further evidenced by lowering in pH in comparison with the binary versus ternary systems, and non-appearance of solid phase during titration. The order of stability of ternary complexes in terms of metal ions and ligands are: $\text{Ni}^{II} < \text{Cu}^{II} > \text{Zn}^{II}$; MALEA > MALNA > PHA (for Ni^{II}) and MALEA > MALNA (for Zn^{II}). The maximum stability of ternary complexes of maleic acid may be due to the presence of a double bond which increases the stability due to exocyclic conjugation.

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Nickel(II), Copper(II) and Manganese(II) Complexes with Tetradentate Schiff Bases and Neutral Ligands

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THE Schiff base complexes of transition metal ions possess unusual configuration¹ and structural lability and are sensitive to molecular environment. Generally, the stable stereochemistries are

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obtained through dimerisation. In continuation of our work in this field, we report here the nature and geometry by divalent nickel, copper and manganese with Schiff bases in presence of neutral monodentate ligands of varying donor atoms.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The Schiff bases, viz. bis-salicylaldehyde ethylenediamine and bis-*o*-hydroxyacetophenone ethylenediamine were prepared by the reported method³. The metals were estimated by standard methods⁵. Sulphur was estimated as BaSO₄ by oxidation with KMnO₄ and concentrated HNO₃. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 grating spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (MeOH) on a Elico CL 24 spectrophotometer. The conductance measurement was carried out in ~ 10⁻³ M solution of nitrobenzene with a Systronics-303 direct reading conductivity meter. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out at room temperature by a Gouy balance using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as the calibrant. Diamagnetic corrections were made by Pascal's constants⁴. The molecular weights were determined by Rast's biphenyl method. The analytical and physical data are given in Table 1.

Preparation of complexes: To a weighed amount of NiCl₂·6H₂O, CuCl₂·2H₂O or MnCl₂·4H₂O, was added a calculated amount of bis-salicylaldehyde ethylenediamine/bis-*o*-hydroxyacetophenone ethylenediamine in 1 : 1 molar ratio in

ethanolic medium and stirred. To it an ethanolic solution of pyridine-*N*-oxide, γ -picoline or hot ethanolic solution of thiourea was added in excess with constant stirring. The solid complexes formed were washed with ethanol and ether and dried under reduced pressure.

Results and Discussion

The compounds formed are microcrystalline solids. The analytical data are consistent with the formulation of the compounds. The conductance values (0.65–4.9 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹) show that the compounds are non-electrolytes. The molecular weight measurement indicates that the compounds are monomeric. The nickel complexes exhibit the magnetic moment values (Table 1) as expected for octahedral nickel(II) complexes⁶. The magnetic measurement values for the copper(II) complexes are consistent with that of 3d⁹ system⁶. The magnetic moments for the manganese(II) complexes suggest high-spin 3d⁵ configuration⁷.

The Schiff bases exhibit a sharp band at ~ 1 630 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{C-N} . This band shifts to a lower frequency by 5–15 cm⁻¹ on complexation due to the reduction of electron density in the azomethine links. The absence of stretching and bending modes of OH group in the spectra indicates the deprotonation of the ligands in the complexes. These observations were supported by the shift of ν_{C-O} of the free ligand from ~ 1 320 to 1 285 $\pm$ (5–15) cm⁻¹. The coordination of the Schiff bases

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Analyses % : Found/(Calcd.)		μ_{eff} B.M.	Λ_M Ω^{-1} cm ² mol ⁻¹	Mol. wt. Found/ (Calcd.)
			Metal	S			
[Ni(sal ₂ en)(γ -pic)]	Sky blue	>250	13.12 (13.98)	—	3.43	0.89	369.8 (419.77)
[Ni(sal ₂ en)(pyNo)]	Yellow	>250	13.11 (13.53)	—	3.44	0.65	366.9 (433.7)
[Ni(sal ₂ en)(tu) ₂]	Brown	>250	12.19 (12.26)	29.12 (30.14)	3.29	0.91	400.0 (428.7)
[Ni(<i>o</i> -hy ₂ en)(γ -pic)]	Sky blue	>250	13.01 (13.11)	—	3.45	2.5	391.5 (447.77)
[Ni(<i>o</i> -hy ₂ en)(pyNo)]	Dirty yellow	>250	11.95 (12.71)	—	3.28	1.5	366.05 (461.7)
[Ni(<i>o</i> -hy ₂ en)(tu) ₂]	Brown	>250	10.89 (11.58)	29.15 (30.33)	3.25	1.4	460.0 (506.7)
[Cu(sal ₂ en)(γ -pic)]	Blue	190	13.93 (14.95)	—	2.18	1.2	381.5 (424.57)
[Cu(sal ₂ en)(pyNo)]	Green	155	13.95 (14.48)	—	2.15	4.2	368.15 (438.5)
[Cu(sal ₂ en)(tu) ₂]	Light green	163	12.99 (13.13)	29.16 (30.18)	1.98	3.2	367.5 (483.5)
[Cu(<i>o</i> -hy ₂ en)(γ -pic)]	Blue	183	13.85 (14.02)	—	2.13	4.5	400.0 (452.61)
[Cu(<i>o</i> -hy ₂ en)(pyNo)]	Light green	165	13.03 (13.69)	—	2.15	3.8	383.21 (466.54)
[Mn(sal ₂ en)(γ -pic) ₂]	Yellow	>250	10.51 (10.79)	—	5.85	2.1	480.0 (509.08)
[Mn(<i>o</i> -hy ₂ en)(γ -pic) ₂]	White	>250	10.11 (10.22)	—	5.93	4.4	498.0 (537.08)
[Mn(<i>o</i> -hy ₂ en)(pyNo) ₂]	Dirty white	>250	9.36 (9.72)	—	5.82	4.9	500.0 (564.94)

through oxygen and nitrogen to metal ions is further indicated by the appearance of ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N} at 440–455 and 610–625 cm^{-1} respectively. Thus, the Schiff bases behave as bifunctional tetradentate (ONNO donor) ligands^{9–11}. The presence of coordinated ν -picoline in the complexes is known from their $\nu_{C-C} + \nu_{C-N}$ bands found at 1 530–1 540 cm^{-1} . The other bands were masked by the Schiff base bands. In the compounds containing thiourea, the ν_{C-S} band shifted to lower frequency (710–720 cm^{-1}) indicating its coordination through sulphur atom¹². The shifting of ν_{N-O} band of pyridine-*N*-oxide from 1 265 to 1 205–1 215 cm^{-1} and δ_{N-O} band from 840 to 845–850 cm^{-1} indicate its bonding to the metal ions through the oxygen atom¹³.

The four Ni(SB)L compounds were found to exhibit absorption bands in the region 13 071–16 393 cm^{-1} which support a pentacoordinated geometry¹⁴. No absorption band for these compounds was found above 17 000 cm^{-1} . Absorption bands due to the two Ni(SB)L₂ compounds at 12 195–12 345, 15 598–15 748 and 25 974–26 315 cm^{-1} may be assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively, for octahedral stereochemistry of divalent nickel¹⁵. The Cu(SB)L compounds were found to exhibit band at 16 129–16 260 cm^{-1} which supports the pentacoordinated stereochemistry^{16,17}. A broad band at 15 873 cm^{-1} for Cu(SB)L₂ complex indicates a distorted octahedral configuration^{18–20}. Bands due to the three manganese(II) compounds at 25 974–26 666, 22 470–23 809 and 17 543–17 699 cm^{-1} support octahedral configuration²¹. Thus, pentacoordinated Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} and hexacoordinated Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Mn^{II} compounds containing bifunctional tetradentate Schiff bases and neutral N, O or S donor ligands are reported.

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Transition Metal Complexes with 4-Amino-5-mercapto-3-methyl-1,2,4-triazole and 8-Hydroxyquinoline

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WE report here the syntheses and characterisation of a few mixed ligand complexes of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II} and VO^{II} with 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-methyl-1,2,4-triazole and 8-hydroxyquinoline. The complexes are expected to have potentialities as insecticides and pesticides.

Experimental

4-Amino-5-mercapto-3-methyl-1,2,4-triazole was prepared according to the literature method¹ by cyclisation of thiocarbohydrazide with glacial acetic acid.

A hot aqueous solution of the ligand (AMMT) (1 mmol) was added to an aqueous solution of the metal chloride (1 mmol) with constant stirring. To the resulting mixture, 8-hydroxyquinoline (1 mmol) in ethanol (55%) was added dropwise. The resulting coloured precipitates separated immediately, were kept on a water-bath for 30 min and filtered hot. The complexes were dried over fused calcium chloride (Table 1).

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 398 spectrophotometer and electronic (DMF) spectra on a Beckmann 35 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility was determined at room temperature by the Gouy method². Thermogravimetric analyses were carried out on a Netzsch 429 instrument at the rate of 10° min⁻¹ in air taking 100 mg of the sample. Conductivity was measured on a Toshniwal conductivity bridge and a dip type cell (cell constant=0.639, concentration of the solution 1 × 10⁻³ M in DMF).